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● *Sinolucanus* nom. nov., a new replacement name for *Xizangia* Zhang, 1988 (Coleoptera: Lucanidae)

Cheng-Bin WANG¹ & Tian-Long HE^{2*}

¹Engineering Research Center for Forest and Grassland Disaster Prevention and Reduction, Mianyang Normal University, Mianyang 621000, Sichuan Province, China; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7913-8779>; entomologist@qq.com

²Donghuaxincheng, Wangfenggang, Xiejiaji District, Huainan 232046, Anhui Province, China; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7301-5105>; htl1988@qq.com

*Corresponding author

Abstract: *Xizangia* Zhang, 1988 was established for *Xizangia cryptonychus* Zhang, 1988 (Coleoptera: Lucanidae). The generic name *Xizangia*, however, is a junior homonym of *Xizangia* Zhang, 1982 (Loftusiida: Orbitolinidae), and we propose a new replacement name, *Sinolucanus* **nom. nov.**

Keywords: Homonym, Lucaninae, new combinations, Penichrolucanini, stag beetle

● 藏毗锹属之新名——中华蚁锹属（鞘翅目：锹甲科）

王成斌¹ & 贺天龙^{2*}

¹森林与草原防灾减灾工程研究中心，绵阳师范学院，绵阳 621000，四川省，中国

²东华鑫城，望峰岗，谢家集区，淮南 232046，安徽省，中国

*通讯作者

摘要：藏毗锹属 *Xizangia* Zhang, 1988 是为藏毗锹 *Xizangia cryptonychus* Zhang, 1988 而建立（鞘翅目：锹甲科）。但该属名 *Xizangia* 为西藏螳属 *Xizangia* Zhang, 1982（Loftusiida: Orbitolinidae）之次同名，本文因而提出了一新替代名：中华蚁锹属 *Sinolucanus* **nom. nov.**。

关键词：异物同名，锹甲亚科，新组合，隐爪锹族，锹甲

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Introduction

Xizangia Zhang, 1988 (Coleoptera: Lucanidae) was established for *Xizangia cryptonychus* Zhang, 1988 from southeast Xizang of China, however, it was misplaced in the family Trogidae (Zhang 1988). Almost five years later, Araya *et al.* (1993) identified *Xizangia* Zhang, 1988 as a member of Lucanidae and synonymized it with *Penichorlucanus* Deyrolle, 1863. Recently, *Xizangia* Zhang, 1988 was revalidated and a second species, *Xizangia qiuae* Huang & Chen, 2022 was described from Yunnan of China (Huang & Chen 2022). However, although Huang & Chen (2022) mentioned *Xizangia* Song, Zhu & Zhang, 2004 (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) is a junior homonym of *Xizangia* Zhang, 1988, they still overlooked that the name “*Xizangia*” had already been used by Zhang (1982) for the Upper Carboniferous foraminifer *Xizangia machalensis* Zhang, 1982, and thus represents a junior homonym (ICZN 1999: Article 56.1). According to ICZN (1999: Article 60.3), the junior name is permanently invalid and has to be replaced. Therefore, here we propose a new substitute name for the junior homonym.

In addition, another spider generic name *Xizangia* Song, Zhu & Zhang, 2004 (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) is also a junior homonym of *Xizangia* Zhang, 1982 and *Xizangia* Zhang, 1988 (see Zhang 1982; Zhang 1988; Song, Zhu & Zhang 2004), but was already replaced as *Xizangiana* Sherwood, Li & Zhang, 2022 (Sherwood *et al.* 2022).

Taxonomy

Genus *Sinolucanus* nom. nov. 中华蚁锹属

<https://zoobank.org/90034530-8B05-4DD0-9567-BDD28AAF9791>

Fig. 1

Xizangia Zhang, 1988: 233, 236 (type species: *Xizangia cryptonychus* Zhang, 1988), nec †*Xizangia* Zhang, 1982: 192, 214 (type species: †*Xizangia machalensis* Zhang, 1982).

Type species. *Xizangia cryptonychus* Zhang, 1988: 234, 236, by present designation.

Included species: *Sinolucanus cryptonychus* (Zhang, 1988) **comb. nov.** and *Sinolucanus qiuae* (Huang & Chen, 2022) **comb. nov.**

Etymology. The generic name is a combination of “*Sino-*” from Latin “*Sinae*” (China) and the genus name “*lucanus*”. The gender is masculine.

FIGURE 1. Black-and-white drawing of dorsal habitus of *Sinolucanus cryptonychus* (Zhang, 1988) **comb. nov.** (after Zhang (1988))

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Additional information

Author contributions: Conceptualization: C-B Wang. Project administration: C-B Wang. Resources: T-L He. Supervision: T-L He. Visualization: C-B Wang. Writing—original draft: C-B Wang. Writing—review and editing: C-B Wang & T-L He.

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